

Bridging Gaps in Distributed Space Systems: A Digital Twin Solution

Angel Pan Du^{1*}, Citlali Bruce Rosete¹, M. Amin Alandihallaj¹, Andreas M. Hein¹

¹Space Systems Engineering (SpaSys) Research Group, Interdisciplinary Centre for Security, Reliability and Trust (SnT), University of Luxembourg

*Phone: +34 625 77 58 84, Mail: angel.pandu@uni.lu

Abstract: This paper presents a conceptual design for an advanced simulator leveraging digital twins, focusing on the subsystems of small satellites and their interdependencies. Existing simulators face challenges due to computational intensity, lack of flexibility, and inability to adapt to dynamic satellite missions. The proposed digital twin-based simulator offers a lightweight, computationally efficient alternative, enabling detailed analysis of mission requirements, iterative design processes, and comprehensive operational assessments. A review of existing Distributed Space Systems (DSS) applications highlights ongoing efforts and completed missions involving small satellites, identifying significant gaps in imaging and surface analysis. These gaps arise from increased complexity in coordination, data synchronization issues, and higher maintenance costs, which currently outweigh the advantages of DSS. To address these gaps, the study proposes developing adaptable digital twins for all satellite subsystems, accurately modeling interdependencies and interactions to establish a robust DSS framework.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the concept of Distributed Space Systems (DSS) has emerged as a revolutionary approach in space technology. These systems involve multiple spacecraft working in a coordinated manner to achieve a common objective, offering enhanced capabilities compared to a single satellite. This technique is particularly significant for Earth observation, as it allows for more comprehensive data collection and improved spatial and temporal resolution [1]. Consequently, DSS are crucial for a myriad of applications, including environmental monitoring, disaster management, urban planning, and climate change studies.

The advent of small satellites has further transformed the landscape of space exploration and observation. As the NewSpace paradigm, which emphasizes cost-effective, rapid, and innovative approaches to space missions [2], small satellites have become enablers and have democratized access to space, enabling a broader range of entities, including universities, startups, and developing countries, to participate in space activities.

This article will delve into the current state of DSS and, in particular, DSS of small satellites. The missions and concepts found in this review aim to enhance the ability to monitor and understand our planet with greater precision and frequency. This capability is essential for making informed decisions that impact both local and global scales.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to reviews by Saptarshi Bandyopadhyay et al. [3, 4], there is a significant focus on Earth observation within the area of DSS of small satellites. These missions have proven to be invaluable for various applications, including ionosphere measurements [5-8], multi-spectral imaging [9, 10], electrical field sensing [11], magnetosphere studies [12-15], aeronomy and geodesy measurements [16, 17], extreme weather prediction [18], Low Earth Orbit (LEO) radiation environment [19-21], Fourier Transform spectrometer

for long-term weather forecast [22], lower thermosphere and re-entry research [23-25], space situational awareness [26, 27], and geophysical monitoring [28-30].

A review of ongoing missions and conceptual studies highlights the innovative approaches and technological advancements in the field of DSS of small satellites. The matrix presented in Figure 1 provides a comprehensive review and categorizes the re-viewed works based on their applications and the satellite subsystems they focus on. Novel studies are also included and categorized as technology demonstrators. Additionally, the status of the mission is highlighted, as they can be completed, ongoing, failed, conceptual or uninitiated missions. This structured approach to the review not only facilitates a clearer understanding of the current state of DSS but also identifies potential areas for future research and development.

Various ongoing missions and conceptual studies have been explored, highlighting the innovative approaches and technological advancements in this field. To provide a comprehensive overview, a matrix is presented in Figure 1, categorizing these reviewed works based on their applications and the satellite subsystems they focus on. Each row represents a different application, such as electromagnetic field studies, imaging, surface analysis, atmosphere and weather studies, or space debris, while each column categorizes the studies according to the satellite subsystem of focus. Moreover, completed and ongoing missions are highlighted with green borders, failed missions with red, and conceptual or uninitiated missions with no border. Additionally, novel studies are included in a dedicated row under technology demonstrators. This structured approach not only facilitates a clearer understanding of the current state of DSS but also identifies potential areas for future research and development.

APPLICATION	Overall	Mission	ADCS	Comm-unications	Payload	Struc-tures	Thermal	Data Handling	Propul-sion	SUBSYSTEM
Electromagnetic field studies	[5] [6] [7] [11] [12] [15]	[19] [20] [21] [14] [31]			[13] [19] [32]			[31]		
Imaging	[33] [34]	[11] [35] [36]	[10] [35] [36]							
Surface analysis	[30] [33]	[16] [28]	[16] [29] [37]		[16] [17]	[17]	[17]			
Atmosphere and weather studies	[22] [38]	[16] [23] [24] [8] [39]	[16] [40]	[18] [25]	[16] [17]	[17]	[17]			
Technology demonstrator	[41] [42]		[43] [44] [45] [46] [47] [48] [49] [50] [51] [52] [53]	[54] [55]	[56] [57]				[58] [59] [50]	

LEGEND

- Completed
- Failed
- 2 satellites
- 3 satellites
- 4 satellites
- 5-15 satellites
- >15 satellites

Figure 1: Matrix from the reviewed literature in DSS

The matrix reveals a significant number of missions dedicated to electromagnetic field studies, indicating a strong interest in this application, and this trend is evident across the overall subsystems. The prevalence of these can be attributed to several advantages offered by DSS [60], mainly the spatial distribution, which enhances the ability to study complex and dynamic processes that would be difficult to capture with a single satellite.

Another area with a significant focus in the matrix is atmosphere and weather studies, which also demonstrates a fine focus across various satellite subsystems. The reason

could be explained with one of the primary benefits of using this technology, which is the ability to achieve high temporal and spatial resolution. By deploying multiple satellites, researchers can obtain simultaneous measurements from different locations, providing a more detailed and dynamic picture of atmospheric conditions for accurately modeling weather patterns and predicting changes [61]. Furthermore, the redundancy offered by DSS ensures continuous data collection, even if one satellite encounters an issue. This reliability is essential for long-term atmospheric monitoring, where consistent and uninterrupted data is necessary for accurate analysis and forecasting.

While the matrix highlights several applications with a significant number of missions, it also reveals areas with fewer missions, such as imaging, surface analysis, and space debris. Understanding the reasons behind this disparity can provide valuable insights into the challenges and emerging trends in these fields. For imaging and surface analysis, the relatively lower number of missions can be attributed to the specific requirements and challenges associated with these applications. High-resolution imaging and detailed surface analysis often demand advanced sensors and precise calibration, which can be more challenging to achieve with DSS [62]. Additionally, the need for stable and synchronized positioning of multiple satellites to capture coherent images can complicate mission design and execution, due to the need of accurate post-processing [63]. These technical and operational challenges may limit the number of missions dedicated to these applications.

Among these missions, it is noteworthy that the majority are designed for systems of two satellites, although some involve three or four. Nonetheless, only a few missions involve larger formations. Moreover, it is noticeable that almost all missions involving more than four satellites remain conceptual, indicating a lack of further development and implementation for large satellite formations. This highlights the need for continued research and innovation to advance the practical deployment of extensive satellite constellations.

Regarding the technology demonstrators, remarkable advancements are driven by these innovative concepts aimed at enhancing their performance and capabilities. Among these, the ADCS stands out as a pivotal domain of focus. This subsystem is crucial for maintaining the precise orientation and positioning of satellites, which is essential for successful mission outcomes, and as described in the previous subsections, there are currently a vast array of methodologies for this purpose.

5. DIGITAL TWIN CONCEPT

A digital twin is a highly sophisticated virtual replica of a physical system that mirrors its characteristics, behaviors, and dynamics. The key to this technology consists of the continuous assimilation of real-time data from its physical counterpart. Digital twins have become an advantageous tool for predictive maintenance, real-time monitoring, and process optimization in industries such as manufacturing, energy, and aerospace in the industry of today. Through the process of continuously updating real-time information, digital twins enable engineers and decision-makers to simulate operations, experiment with scenarios, and predict failures before they occur.

Consequently, these high-fidelity models offer numerous benefits due to their data-driven approach. By integrating real-time sensor information, digital twins provide robust predictive maintenance functionalities, enabling systems to respond quickly to operational changes and anticipate potential complications. Their simulation environments are designed to be lightweight yet comprehensive, enabling rigorous operational and design optimization with minimal computational overhead. This ensures that changes in one

subsystem are rapidly reflected throughout the model, facilitating an in-depth analysis of interdependencies. Moreover, the modularity of these systems supports scalability and interoperability, ultimately reducing development costs and operational risks by allowing exhaustive virtual testing that replicates true conditions with high accuracy.

The architecture of a spacecraft digital twin can be conceptualized through a multi-layered structure, as seen in Figure 2, consisting of four main dimensions:

- **Physical entity:** This represents the real satellite, offering the basis for the digital twin, encompassing all hardware elements and physical aspects.
- **Virtual entity:** Being the digital counterpart, this involves the comprehensive simulation of the physical entity, mimicking key parameters such as satellite dynamics and orbital behaviors.
- **Data layer:** Located at the core of the system, this layer aggregates simulation, sensor, and telemetry data. It serves as the foundation of predictive and analytical capabilities of the digital twin, by providing a robust dataset for continuous monitoring and simulation.
- **Communication network:** Enables data exchange between the physical and virtual systems. Beyond the individual satellite, this constitutes a network of interconnected spacecraft to facilitate cooperation among several spacecraft. It is designed to ensure scalability and interoperability such that a DSS can be operated as a single unit.

Figure 2: Four-dimensional model of spacecraft digital twin

However, currently some challenges make their widespread practical implementation difficult. Processing real-time data efficiently is a major challenge, since high accuracy is required, which could lead to a potential cost increase that should be weighed against the benefits. Furthermore, security concerns must also be addressed, given the sensitivity of satellite data and the risks associated with cyber threats. Finally, validation and verification of digital twin models to ensure they are trustworthy throughout a mission life cycle is an ongoing and technically demanding process.

The proposed digital twin for a satellite is sketched in Figure 3, where all the interconnections between subsystems can be observed. As appreciated, the power subsystem is the central node, integrating power consumption data from the other main subsystems, the attitude determination and control system (ADCS), the on-board computer (OBC), the thermal, the propulsion, the payload, and the telemetry, tracking, and command system (TT&C). The ADCS and OBC work together to determine the optimal attitude, based on the pointing requirements defined by TT&C or the payload, to position the satellite. Moreover, accurate orbit propagation and disturbance calculations further depend on the

attitude data and consumed propellant mass, with the resulting position data feeding back to both the ADCS and thermal subsystems.

Up to this point, the framework could be used for a conventional simulator. Nevertheless, the digital twin aspect is facilitated through the addition of live sensor data – primarily impacting ADCS, orbit dynamics, and power monitoring – which refines the simulation. A dynamic data fusion mechanism, through techniques such as adaptive weighting and filtering, would help prioritize real-time sensor inputs over predicted data, in order to alleviate problems such as sensor noise and latency without compromising high-fidelity in the model.

Figure 3: Digital twin satellite subsystems interdependencies flowchart

For extrapolating to a DSS digital twin, each satellite would maintain its own digital twin with the same modular design and operate as previously described. These individual digital twin nodes are interconnected through a robust communication network, which gathers real-time sensor data and simulation outputs from all satellites, being also the foundational data exchange point from the physical and virtual entities. This intermediate DSS layer enables coordinated operations, and inter-satellite data transfer is utilized to facilitate joint maneuver planning, dynamically adapt to changing mission requirements, collision avoidance, maintain optimal formation geometry, and synchronized task execution.

Control requirements and actuator management are of paramount importance in this framework, particularly relative positioning between satellites. To achieve coordinated maneuvers and formation flight, the system would utilize Clohessy-Wiltshire (CW) equations to model the relative dynamics between satellites. Thus, the generated precise control commands for actuators, such as thrusters and reaction wheels, are transferred to each satellite. These actuators would position and orient the satellite, ensuring that the relative positioning remains within the required tolerances.

By integrating these elements into the overall digital twin architecture as seen in the scheme in Figure 4, the framework would facilitate both real-time operating adjustments and high-fidelity simulations, enhancing performance and reliability of DSS.

Figure 4: Digital twin communication network scheme for DSS

6. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has explored the existing gaps in Distributed Space Systems (DSS), particularly the lack of integrated subsystem modeling, limited adaptability in mission design, and challenges in coordinating formation-level operations. In response to these limitations, this work proposes a novel digital twin framework that emphasizes modularity, subsystem interconnectivity, and adaptability to a wide range of mission scenarios. By accurately modeling the interdependencies among all satellite subsystems, the framework provides better insights into both system-level behavior and individual satellite dynamics.

Extension to formation flying allows for coordinated operations and joint task execution, helping to overcome key challenges in DSS such as synchronization and control complexity. This software would be designed to facilitate iterative mission design and performance analysis while remaining computationally lightweight. Moreover, to demonstrate its applicability, a case study within the GLITTER project [64] would showcase how the framework can be employed to support GNSS-R missions using CubeSat formations and beamforming, addressing existing gaps in high-resolution surface analysis. Overall, the proposed digital twin solution offers significant advancement towards bridging current gaps in DSS, enabling more flexible, scalable, and insight-driven satellite mission design.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreement No 101120117. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] Q. Zhao *et al.*, “An Overview of the Applications of Earth Observation Satellite Data: Impacts and Future Trends,” *Remote Sens (Basel)*, vol. 14, no. 8, 2022, doi: 10.3390/rs14081863.
- [2] J. L. T. J. and Pelton, “Overview of Commercial Small Satellite Systems in the ‘‘New Space’’ Age,” in *Handbook of Small Satellites: Technology, Design, Manufacture, Applications, Economics and Regulation*, J. Pelton, Ed., Springer International Publishing, 2019, pp. 1–18. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-20707-6_4-1.
- [3] S. Bandyopadhyay, G. P. Subramanian, R. Foust, D. Morgan, S.-J. Chung, and F. Hadaegh, “A Review of Impending Small Satellite Formation Flying Missions,” in *53rd AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting*, 2015, pp. 1–17. doi: 10.2514/6.2015-1623.
- [4] S. Bandyopadhyay, R. Foust, G. P. Subramanian, S.-J. Chung, and F. Y. Hadaegh, “Review of Formation Flying and Constellation Missions Using Nanosatellites,” *J Spacecr Rockets*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 567–578, 2016, doi: 10.2514/1.A33291.
- [5] G. Crowley *et al.*, “Dynamic Ionosphere Cubesat Experiment (DICE),” in *25th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, Mar. 2011.
- [6] C. Fish *et al.*, “DICE Mission Design, Development, and Implementation: Success and Challenges,” in *26th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, Mar. 2012.
- [7] P. Bracikowski, K. A. Lynch, and L. Gayetsky, “Low-resource cubesat-scale sensorcraft for auroral and ionospheric plasma studies,” in *24th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, Mar. 2010.
- [8] A. J. Mannucci, J. Dickson, C. Duncan, and K. Hurst, “GNSS Geospace Constellation (GGC): a CubeSat space weather mission concept,” 2010.
- [9] C. J. Lowe, M. Macdonald, S. Greenland, and D. Mecke, “Charybdis: The next generation in ocean colour and biogeochemical remote sensing,” in *26th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, Mar. 2012.

- [10] K. Riesing and K. Cahoy, "Propagation of CubeSats in LEO using NORAD two line element sets: Accuracy and update frequency," in *29th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, 2015. doi: 10.2514/6.2013-4944.
- [11] F. Redd and T. Olsen, "Microspacecraft and earth observation-The electrical field (ELF) measurement project," in *Space Programs and Technologies Conference*, Mar. 1990.
- [12] D. Clarke *et al.*, "Picosat Free Flying Magnetometer Experiment," in *10th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, Mar. 1996.
- [13] M. C. Wilz, "Focused investigations of relativistic electron burst intensity, range, and dynamics space weather mission global positioning system," Montana State University, 2011.
- [14] J. P. Eastwood, "Observing Magnetic Reconnection: The Influence of Jim Dungey," in *Magnetospheric Plasma Physics: The Impact of Jim Dungey's Research*, S. W. H. Cowley FRS, D. Southwood, and S. Mitton, Eds., Springer International Publishing, 2015, pp. 181–197. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-18359-6_9.
- [15] H. Bahcivan, K. Leveque, and R. ~A. Doe, "Cubesat-Based Dtv Receiver Constellation for Ionospheric Tomography," in *AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts*, Mar. 2013.
- [16] J. Conklin *et al.*, "Small Satellite Constellations for Earth Geodesy and Aeronomy," in *27th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, Mar. 2013.
- [17] C. Zanoni *et al.*, "The Design of a Drag-Free CubeSat and the Housing for its Gravitational Reference Sensor," *IAA Technical Session XII: CubeSat Design and Payload*, Mar. 2016.
- [18] S. Padmanabhan *et al.*, "A 6U CubeSat constellation for atmospheric temperature and humidity sounding," in *27th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, Mar. 2013.
- [19] A. Gunderson *et al.*, "Simultaneous Multi-Point Space Weather Measurements Using the Low Cost EDSN CubeSat Constellation," in *27th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, Mar. 2013.
- [20] B. Yost, "EDSN-edison demonstration for smallsat networks overview," in *27th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, Mar. 2013.
- [21] D. Westley, "EDSN-Edison Demonstration for SmallSat Networks EDSN Overview," 2015.
- [22] P. Wloszek *et al.*, "FTS CubeSat constellation providing 3D winds," in *27th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, Mar. 2013.
- [23] H. Bedon, C. Negron, J. Llantoy, C. Miguel Nieto, and C. O. Asma, "Preliminary internetworking simulation of the QB50 cubesat constellation," in *2010 IEEE Latin-American Conference on Communications*, 2010, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/LATINCOM.2010.5640977.
- [24] E. Gill, P. Sundaramoorthy, J. Bouwmeester, B. Zandbergen, and R. Reinhard, "Formation flying within a constellation of nano-satellites: The QB50 mission," *Acta Astronaut*, vol. 82, no. 1, pp. 110–117, Mar. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.actaastro.2012.04.029.
- [25] G. March, T. Scholz, J. Thömel, P. Rambaud, S. Marcuccio, and others, "Challenges and Solutions for the QB50 Telecommunication Network," in *27th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, Mar. 2014.
- [26] M. R. Tetlow and T. Chin, "Robust Attitude Estimation to Support Space Monitoring Using Nano-Satellites," in *AIAA SPACE 2014 Conference and Exposition*, 2014. doi: 10.2514/6.2014-4293.
- [27] K. Morris, C. Rice, and M. Wolfson, "CubeSat integration into the space situational awareness architecture," in *Advanced Maui Optical and Space Surveillance Conference, Hawaii, USA: AMOS*, 2013, pp. 1–11.
- [28] E. Peterson, R. Zee, and G. Fotopoulos, "Possible orbit scenarios for an InSAR formation flying microsatellite mission," in *22th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, Mar. 2008.
- [29] N. Orr, J. Eyer, J. Grzymisch, and R. Zee, "Precision Formation Flight: The CanX-4 and CanX-5 Dual Nanosatellite Mission," in *21th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, Mar. 2007.
- [30] G. Bonin, N. Roth, S. Armitage, J. Newman, B. Risi, and R. E. Zee, "SSC15-I-4 CanX-4 and CanX-5 Precision Formation Flight: Mission Accomplished!," in *29th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites*, 2015.
- [31] R. B. Torbert *et al.*, "The FIELDS Instrument Suite on MMS: Scientific Objectives, Measurements, and Data Products," *Space Sci Rev*, vol. 199, no. 1, pp. 105–135, 2016, doi: 10.1007/s11214-014-0109-8.
- [32] R. E. Ergun *et al.*, "The Axial Double Probe and Fields Signal Processing for the MMS Mission," *Space Sci Rev*, vol. 199, no. 1, pp. 167–188, 2016, doi: 10.1007/s11214-014-0115-x.
- [33] G. Krieger *et al.*, "TanDEM-X: A satellite formation for high-resolution SAR interferometry," in *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, Nov. 2007, pp. 3317–3340. doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2007.900693.
- [34] S. Persson, S. Veldman, and P. Bodin, "PRISMA—A formation flying project in implementation phase," *Acta Astronaut*, vol. 65, no. 9, pp. 1360–1374, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.actaastro.2009.03.067.
- [35] D. Galano *et al.*, "Proba-3 precise formation flying mission," in *International Workshop on Satellites Constellations and Formation Flying (IWSCFF), Glasgow, United Kingdom*, 2019.

- [36] M. Landgraf and A. Mestreau-Garreau, "Formation flying and mission design for Proba-3," *Acta Astronaut*, vol. 82, no. 1, pp. 137–145, 2013, doi: j.actaastro.2012.03.028.
- [37] F. Scala, C. Colombo, G. Gaias, and M. martin-neira, "Three Satellites Formation Flying: Deployment and Formation Acquisition Using Relative Orbital Elements.," in *2020 AAS/AIAA Astrodynamics Specialist Conference*, Mar. 2020.
- [38] R. P. Kornfeld *et al.*, "GRACE-FO: The Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment Follow-On Mission," *J Spacecr Rockets*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 931–951, 2019, doi: 10.2514/1.A34326.
- [39] A. and C. W. F. and Q. N. and M. C. and B. T. Kelly Angelita C. and Loverro, "Small Earth Observing Satellites Flying with Large Satellites in the A-Train," in *Small Satellite Missions for Earth Observation*, H.-P. and V. A. Sandau Rainer and Roeser, Ed., Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2010, pp. 19–28.
- [40] X. Guo, Y. Zhang, H. Zhou, Y. Zhao, and Q. Zhao, "Enhanced orbit determination for formation-flying satellites based on M-estimation," *Advances in Space Research*, vol. 70, no. 4, pp. 923–934, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.asr.2022.05.043.
- [41] L. Liangsheng, M. Jian, C. Junli, L. Zhiming, Z. Xiaowei, and Z. Hao, "Key issues of InSAR system designment based on satellite formation," *Acta Geodaetica et Cartographica Sinica*, vol. 51, no. 7, 2022, doi: 10.11947/j.AGCS.2022.20220110.
- [42] F. Y. Hadaegh, S.-J. Chung, and H. M. Manohara, "On Development of 100-Gram-Class Spacecraft for Swarm Applications," *IEEE Syst J*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 673–684, 2016, doi: 10.1109/JSYST.2014.2327972.
- [43] A. Caruso, A. A. Quarta, G. Mengali, and M. Bassetto, "Optimal On-Orbit Inspection of Satellite Formation," *Remote Sens (Basel)*, vol. 14, no. 20, 2022, doi: 10.3390/rs14205192.
- [44] X. Zuo, X. Pan, M. Xu, L. Ma, and J. Zhang, "Deployment strategy for satellite-sail transverse formation," *Acta Astronaut*, vol. 186, pp. 242–251, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.actaastro.2021.05.031.
- [45] H. Cho, "Energy-optimal reconfiguration of satellite formation flying in the presence of uncertainties," *Advances in Space Research*, vol. 67, no. 5, pp. 1454–1467, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.asr.2020.11.036.
- [46] G. Rigatos, M. Abbaszadeh, J. Pomares, P. Siano, M. Al-Numay, and G. Cuccurullo, "Nonlinear optimal control for triangular tethered multi-satellite formations," *Advances in Space Research*, vol. 74, no. 3, pp. 1437–1459, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.asr.2024.05.013.
- [47] J. Wang and C. Liu, "The J 2 Relative Perturbation Analysis of Satellite Formation under the Requirement of Relative Position Maintenance with Millimeter-Level Accuracy," *International Journal of Aerospace Engineering*, vol. 2021, pp. 1–9, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1155/2021/6687468.
- [48] W. Gao, K. Li, and C. Wei, "Satellite Cluster Formation Reconfiguration Based on the Bifurcating Potential Field," *Aerospace*, vol. 9, no. 3, 2022, doi: 10.3390/aerospace9030137.
- [49] H. Liao *et al.*, "Compound Attitude Maneuver and Collision Avoiding Control for a Novel Noncontact Close-Proximity Formation Satellite Architecture," *International Journal of Aerospace Engineering*, vol. 2022, no. 1, p. 2606233, 2022.
- [50] J. Y. He, D. H. Chen, and X. C. Liu, "Study on trajectory optimization of satellite rapid orbit formation flying for space object," *J Phys Conf Ser*, vol. 2746, no. 1, p. 12005, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/2746/1/012005.
- [51] X. Mi *et al.*, "Absolute and relative POD of LEO satellites in formation flying: Undifferenced and uncombined approach," *Advances in Space Research*, vol. 72, no. 4, pp. 1070–1080, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.asr.2023.05.024.
- [52] M. Atallah, M. Okasha, T. N. Dief, and A.-H. Jallad, "Optimal consensus control for multi-satellite assembly in elliptic orbit with input saturation," *Acta Astronaut*, vol. 208, pp. 82–90, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.actaastro.2023.04.006.
- [53] G. Joshi, "Robust and Precision Satellite Formation Flying Guidance Using Adaptive Optimal Control Techniques," 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.01813>
- [54] N. U. L. Hassan, C. Huang, C. Yuen, A. Ahmad, and Y. Zhang, "Dense Small Satellite Networks for Modern Terrestrial Communication Systems: Benefits, Infrastructure, and Technologies," *IEEE Wirel Commun*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 96–103, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1109/MWC.001.1900394.
- [55] R. Deng, B. Di, and L. Song, "Ultra-Dense LEO Satellite Based Formation Flying," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 69, no. 5, pp. 3091–3105, 2021, doi: 10.1109/TCOMM.2021.3058370.
- [56] T. Amiot, F. Douchin, E. Thouvenot, J. C. Souyris, and B. Cugny, "The interferometric cartwheel: a multi-purpose formation of passive radar microsattellites," in *IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, 2002, pp. 435–437 vol.1. doi: 10.1109/IGARSS.2002.1025064.
- [57] X. Li, Z. Yang, S. He, P. Huang, G. Liao, and Y. Jiang, "Nonhomogeneous clutter suppression based on terrain elevation interferometric phase compensation in multi-satellite formation systems," *Digit Signal Process*, vol. 121, p. 103282, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.dsp.2021.103282.

- [58] N. A. Yahya, R. Varatharajoo, A. S. M. Harithuddin, and Y. Razoumny, "Delta-V and ground metric investigations for responsive satellite formation flying," *Acta Astronaut*, vol. 193, pp. 20–34, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.actaastro.2021.12.033.
- [59] Z. Wang, J. Tian, and J. Fu, "Fuel optimization schemes for formation reconfiguration in satellite formation flying," *Advances in Space Research*, vol. 72, no. 5, pp. 1496–1508, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.asr.2023.04.028.
- [60] T. W. Williams, N. Ottenstein, M. Farahmand, and E. Palmer, "Initial Satellite Formation Flight Results from the Magnetospheric Multiscale Mission," in *AIAA/AAS Astrodynamics Specialist Conference*, 2016, doi: 10.2514/6.2016-5505.
- [61] A. Ledkov and V. Aslanov, "Review of contact and contactless active space debris removal approaches," *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, vol. 134, p. 100858, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.paerosci.2022.100858.
- [62] J. Alvarez and B. Walls, "Constellations, clusters, and communication technology: Expanding small satellite access to space," in *2016 IEEE Aerospace Conference*, 2016, pp. 1–11. doi: 10.1109/AERO.2016.7500896.
- [63] S. Nag, C. K. Gatebe, D. W. Miller, and O. L. de Weck, "Effect of satellite formations and imaging modes on global albedo estimation," *Acta Astronaut*, vol. 126, pp. 77–97, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.actaastro.2016.04.004.
- [64] C. Craeye, "Gnss-r sateLIITe earTh obsERvation," Mar. 01, 2024. doi: 10.3030/101120117.